

Stability Constants of Palladium, Copper, Nickel, Zinc and Manganese Complexes of 3-Hydroxy-3-methyl-1-*p*-tolyl and -1-*p*-methoxyphenyltriazenes

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In the previous communication¹, stability constants of palladium, copper, nickel, zinc, and manganese chelates of 3-hydroxy-3-ethyl-1-*p*-chloro and -1-*o*-chlorophenyltriazenes were reported. The present investigation deals with the influence of substituting methyl and methoxy groups at *para* position of the benzene ring of 3-hydroxy-3-methyl-1-phenyltriazenes on the stabilities of metal chelates formed by them.

1. S. M. Dugar and N. C. Sogani, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 646.

EXPERIMENTAL

Hydroxytriazenes have been prepared by the method given by Sogani and Dugar². The stability constants have been determined by employing Bjerrum-Calvin *pH* titration technique³. The titration solution in 70% v/v dioxan-water was 0.1*M*, 0.0002*M*, 0.008*M* with respect to potassium chloride, metal ion and ligand respectively and with sufficient nitric acid to maintain the *pH* at 2. Cambridge bench type *pH*-meter was used to follow the changes in *pH* during the titration with 0.02*M* sodium hydroxide at 25°±0.5°. Other details are the same as described earlier. The titration curves are given in Figs. 1 and 2.

Calculations—The horizontal distance between the reference titration curve and the curve obtained in presence of metal ion gives the amount of metal bound ligand. This value divided by the total metal ion concentration gives the value for \bar{n} . In this way the values of \bar{n} at different *pH* values were calculated. At any *pH*, the value of free ligand ion concentration [T], was calculated from the total ligand concentration [HT], and its dissociation quotient, *pK*_a. This is based on the assumption that the excess of chelating agent over

2. *Idem.*, *ibid.*, 1966, **43**, 289.

3. M. Calvin and N. C. Melchior, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3270

metal ion is so great that the removal of HT by chelation does not cause any significant change in the equilibrium: $\text{HT} \rightleftharpoons \text{H}^+ + \text{T}^-$. The pK_a values of these hydroxytriazenes were determined spectrophotometrically⁴.

In calculating the values for \bar{n} and $[\text{T}]$, the concentrations were corrected for changes in volume produced by the addition of alkali during titrations. In this way a series of values of \bar{n} and $[\text{T}]$, corresponding to different $p\text{H}$ values were obtained and plotted to get the formation curves, given in Figs. 3 and 4.

Fig. 3

The values for $\log k_1$ and $\log k_2$ of nickel, zinc and manganese chelates were directly read from their formation curves. These values for palladium and copper chelates were

Fig. 4

calculated by the method of least-squares⁵. The reason for this has already been discussed in earlier communication. The results are consistent within ± 0.02 and given in Table I.

4. S. M. Dugar and N. C. Sogani, *Z. Naturforschung*, 1966, **21**, 657.

5. J. B. Scarborough, 'Numerical Mathematical Analysis', 4th. Ed., John Hopkins, Baltimore, 1958.

TABLE I

Stabilities of metal chelates of hydroxytriazenes

Metal	Metal chelates of 3-hydroxy-3-methyl-1- <i>p</i> - tolyltriazene			Metal chelates of 3-hydroxy-3-methyl-1- <i>p</i> - methoxyphenyltriazene		
	log k_1	log k_2	log k_1k_2	log k_1	log k_2	log k_1k_2
Palladium	11.77	11.33	23.10	12.25	11.45	23.70
Copper	11.63	10.93	22.56	11.96	11.38	23.33
Nickel	9.43	7.96	17.29	9.57	8.14	17.71
Zinc	7.46	5.86	13.32	7.84	6.06	13.90
Manganese	7.01	5.57	12.58	7.39	5.60	12.99

DISCUSSION

For the sake of simplicity, only the stabilities of palladium chelates with different hydroxytriazenes are discussed. A comparison of the pK_a values of the methyl and methoxy substituted hydroxytriazenes (Table II) with the parent compound⁶ reveals that these groups

TABLE II

 pK_a and log $k_1 k_2$ of palladium chelates of hydroxytriazenes

Hydroxytriazene	pK_a	log k_1k_2
$\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_3\text{—N—OH} \\ \\ \text{N} = \text{N—C}_6\text{H}_5 \end{array}$	12.11	21.92
$\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_3\text{—N—OH} \\ \\ \text{N} = \text{N—C}_6\text{H}_4\text{—CH}_3(p) \end{array}$	12.52	23.10
$\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_3\text{—N—OH} \\ \\ \text{N} = \text{N—C}_6\text{H}_4\text{—OCH}_3(p) \end{array}$	12.69	23.70

in *para* position of the benzene ring have increased the pK_a values. In the former case this is due to +I effect (electron pushing) of the methyl group. A hyperconjugative effect for the methyl group would have a similar influence. In the latter case, +M effect of the methoxy group is responsible for an increased pK_a value. With this increase in the pK_a values of chelating agent, the stabilities of palladium chelates also correspondingly increase. +M effect of the methoxy group seems to play a greater role than +I effect of the methyl group on the pK_a values and the stabilities of metal chelates.

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